

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRESCHOOLERS IN THE CONDITIONS OF FORMATION OF A FAVORABLE ORGANIZATIONAL AND INNOVATIVE ENVIRONMENT

Niyazmetova Iroda Sanjar kizi

2nd year master's student, Puchon University in Tashkent

gaziyevairoda@gmail.com

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Abstract: In this article we consider the psychological features of preschoolers' development occurring in the conditions of an innovative educational environment aimed at their comprehensive development. The main attention is paid to the relationship between the level of innovativeness of teachers of preschool educational organizations and the development of cognitive, emotional-volitional and conative spheres in senior preschool children.

Keywords: psychological characteristics, preschool age, preschool educational organization, organizational and innovative environment, leader, teacher.

Introduction. The problem of forming a favorable organizational and innovative climate in a preschool educational organization has recently increasingly attracted the attention of both teachers and psychologists, scientists and researchers. Successful formation of a favorable organizational and innovative environment and implementation of innovative activities directly depends on the head of the preschool organization and the teaching staff, on their awareness of the innovative idea, since in the conditions of the innovative regime there is an active process of personal growth of the teacher, changes in the nature of relationships between employees of the preschool organization occur.

Main part. It is obvious that successful upbringing and education of preschool children is directly related to the individual, personal and professional qualities of teachers. Such qualities include, for example, organization, focus on results, as well as the desire to improve self-esteem and professional competencies. In the work of Shmeleva E. A. it is noted that "the formation of an organizational and innovative environment is aimed at developing the innovative potential necessary for generating new ideas, creating new products, technologies, promoting fundamental and applied research in various fields of knowledge, including pedagogical, and developing the innovative activity of an individual as the main criterion for readiness for innovative activity in the professional sphere" [1].

The main distinguishing feature of the teaching staff is the specificity of its professional activity, which consists of teaching and educating preschool children. The effectiveness of the teaching staff depends on the level of pedagogical culture of its members, the quality of interpersonal relationships, awareness of collective and individual responsibility, readiness for cooperation, and the degree of organization [2].

Baina M.A. believes that for the effective implementation of educational and upbringing activities in a preschool educational organization, a creative and proactive teacher is required, capable of non-standard, but thoughtful decisions [3]. For this very reason, new requirements are imposed on the preschool teacher, which are largely related to the degree of his professional skills, compliance with the requirements of the state educational standard of preschool education, personal activity, creativity, the ability to self-improvement and self-development, flexibility.

We have put forward the assumption that the general level of development of a preschooler, his cognitive, emotional-volitional and conative spheres of the psyche depends on the degree of formation of innovativeness of each teacher of the preschool educational institution. The effectiveness of the activity of the teaching staff as a whole depends on the determination of the state of innovativeness. In order to test this hypothesis, we conducted an experiment consisting of two stages.

At the first stage, we conducted an express questionnaire with 40 teachers of the preschool educational organization according to the method of V. P. Chudakova [4]. Based on the results of this survey, we identified 2 teachers of the preparatory group for school with the highest and lowest degree of innovation for further study of preschoolers, since the level of development of preschoolers is an indicator of the innovative activity of the teacher and the preschool organization as a whole. During the experiment, various diagnostic methods were used aimed at determining the level of development of the mental spheres of children, namely cognitive, emotional-volitional and conative.

To diagnose the cognitive sphere, the Kern-Jierasek School Maturity Orientation Test method was used, including written and oral tasks aimed at determining readiness for school education. In Group A (with a high level of teacher innovation), 81% of children showed a high level of readiness in the written block, which can be explained by less external stress and greater concentration on the task. And in Group B (with a low level of innovation), this figure was 29%. At the same time, Group B had difficulties in completing written tasks and a low level of readiness in oral form. Despite high motivation, this group demonstrated greater disorganization and a low level of readiness for school education, which can be associated with insufficient innovativeness of the educational environment.

To diagnose the emotional-volitional sphere, the method of "Cooperative-competitive communication with peers" (author G. Zuckerman) was used, aimed at identifying children's ability for emotional empathy and cooperation. In "Group A", 72% of children demonstrated a high level of emotional involvement, which may be associated with the peculiarities of the pedagogical approach that stimulates empathy and support between children. While in "Group B" this figure was 28%, the emotional involvement of preschoolers in this group was lower, which may indicate the need to improve the conditions for the development of emotional intelligence in children, including interaction with teachers and peers. The data obtained indicate a higher level of development in children of "Group A" in terms of recognizing and interpreting the emotions of others.

To diagnose the conative sphere, the "Rukavichka" method (authors Yu. A. Afon'kina, G. A. Uruntaeva) was used, which assessed the level of interaction and cooperation between children. In "Group A", 56% of children demonstrated a high level of interaction, which indicates the ability to work effectively in a group, while in "Group B", 62% of children showed a high level of interaction, which may indicate the development of their conative sphere with less innovative teachers. This may indicate that in kindergarten groups with a high level of children's cognitive skills, a lower level of development of the conative sphere is often observed, which is expressed in the fact that children are less friendly and cohesive. This may be due to a number of factors. Uruntaeva G. A. noted in her works that "children

with a high level of cognitive abilities can be more individualistic, since their interests and ways of thinking may differ from the interests of their peers" [5]. This can cause difficulties for preschoolers in establishing strong emotional connections and interactions with other children, since their ways of perceiving and problem-solving methods may not coincide with the collective approaches of the group, as we have seen with the results of this method.

Discussion of the obtained results. The study showed that the level of formation of innovativeness of the educational environment and pedagogical approach has a significant impact on the development of various mental spheres in preschoolers. In groups with a highly innovative approach, children show better results in the cognitive and emotional spheres, while in less innovative groups there is a more pronounced tendency to cooperation and interaction.

One of the key patterns is that children with a high level of cognitive abilities may be less inclined to cooperate and more individualistic, which hinders the development of their social skills. On the contrary, in groups with a lower level of cognitive development, but a more balanced approach to education, a more harmonious development of the conative sphere is observed, which contributes to better interaction in the team.

Conclusion. The results of the study confirm that the creation of a favorable organizational and innovative environment in a preschool educational organization significantly affects the comprehensive development of older children. The level of innovativeness of teachers and their approach to raising children is directly related to the development of the cognitive, emotional-volitional and conative spheres of preschoolers. An important conclusion is that the successful development of all these spheres requires not only innovative teaching methods, but also the creation of conditions for emotional support and effective cooperation between children.

Thus, innovative approaches in preschool education aimed at individualization and development of the child's personality are of key importance for the formation of a harmonious organizational and innovative environment that promotes the comprehensive development of preschoolers.

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